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WAYS OF DEVELOPING BRANDING PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: Strengthening a business brand to stand out among competitors is a key priority for management today, regardless of the company's form, where assets play a crucial role. Every stakeholder should recognize the significance of this process, as assets particularly the material components are closely tied to conveying the company's brand identity. This article explores one of the fundamental concepts of branding, brand personality, in detail, highlighting its role as an effective communication tool between a company and its consumers.

Key words: asset management, intellectual property, brand personality, educational service, education brand.

INTRODUCTION

To stand out in the market among consumers and investors, every business strives to develop its own strategy to build a strong and effective brand. Otherwise, it risks losing not only profit and prestige but also its market share. A company may hire a skilled leader and a competent team to create a strong brand. However, the primary challenge lies in maintaining and effectively delivering it over a long period, especially as advanced IT and globalization significantly influence brand strengthening by increasing awareness of similar products and services.

Since the external environment has a substantial impact on this process, merely hiring good specialists is not sufficient. A more effective approach involves continuously monitoring the market and seeking adaptive strategies in response to its changes, with a particular focus on intellectual assets. Some years ago, it was uncommon to consider intangible assets in a company's structure, but they now play a crucial role, including trademarks, company names, and other intellectual properties.

The effective management of assets is a key factor in implementing strategic directions for any business operating in the economy. In the past, asset structures focused solely on material elements, but today, the importance of intellectual property and capital is increasing in line with the demands of the innovative economy. The main components of intellectual property (capital) include industrial property, trademarks (brands), company names, customer bases, business reputation, and more.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Enhancing the scientific potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan and introducing it to the global education market contributes to the creation of a competitive environment for students, scholars, and professors in this sector. To determine the priority areas for the systemic reform of higher education in Uzbekistan, it is essential to elevate the process of training highly qualified, independent-thinking professionals with modern knowledge and strong moral and ethical values. This necessitates the modernization of higher education, as well as the development of the social sphere and economic sectors through the application of advanced educational technologies¹. In this context, an effective brand policy must be established in the right direction. A strong brand in a highly competitive environment will help address these challenges.

Prestigious higher education institutions (HEIs) worldwide demonstrate how strong brand management contributes to their successful operation. For example, Oxford University, where teaching has existed in some form since 1096, has developed into a globally recognized institution with four academic divisions encompassing various departments, faculties, and research centers². When discussing university branding, it is important to emphasize that a university's brand embodies the perceptions and experiences of all its stakeholders.

The development of the structure of tertiary education, which directly influences an institution's brand, has been studied by scholars in Uzbekistan. Various academic works have explored different aspects of this topic. In his doctoral dissertation, Professor D. Rahmonov justifies the methodology for determining tuition fees based on scientific potential³ and proposes implementing public-private partnerships as a key strategy

1 On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of Uzbekistan until 2030, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2 <https://www.ox.ac.uk/>

3 D.A. Rahmonov, Improving the methodological foundations of financing the social sphere in Uzbekistan, T: TSUE, 2018, 72 p

for increasing extra-budgetary funding in higher education. Similarly, in her PhD dissertation, N. Zufarova highlights the importance of financial evaluation in the formation of a university brand. She argues that, in the financial balance of a higher education institution, priority should be given to revenue streams such as tuition fees from international students, sponsorships, and extra-budgetary funds from legal entities and individuals⁴.

These scholarly efforts aim to enhance the quality of educational services, align them with global standards, foster a competitive environment, and establish strong institutional branding. Ultimately, a well-developed university brand serves to expand market share within the sector by effectively meeting the needs and expectations of students and other stakeholders.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to have up-to-date results and information, secondary data has been very effective and useful. That's why, in the article, methods such as observation, abstract-logical thinking, and a systematic approach to secondary data have also been used as one of the main methods. There are several types of data collection: conducting face-to-face interviews, focusing group discussions, conducting computer-aided telephonic interviews (CATI), conducting computer-aided web interviews (CAWI), conducting web surveys, and conducting mobile surveys. Mobile surveys are becoming very popular nowadays, as almost everybody, regardless of age and lifestyle, uses smartphones, which allows this type of data collection to spread all over the world. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression is utilized to analyze the hypothesized relationships in the article. To enhance the internal validity of the results, various measures of fulfillment, reliability, and efficiency were examined whenever possible.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As perceived quality refers to students' and graduates' judgments about a higher education institution's overall excellence or superiority (Zeithaml, 1988), where the scientific success of HEI and tuition fees play not the least role; while reputation is the overall value, esteem, and character of a brand as seen or judged by people in general (Chaudhuri, 2002)⁵.

Figure1. Stakeholders of HEI.

Each stakeholder pursues their own goal in the improvement and future development of their organization, where students care about the quality of courses delivered and their influence on job prospects, while professionals worry about the quality of students who have chosen this HEI to study. All stakeholders, without prompting, identified the same issues as being critical to the future development of the university. They were:

⁴ N.G.Zufarova, Improving the management of brand capital in higher education, T: TSUE, 2022.

⁵ The role of brand attachment strength in higher education, Charles Dennis, Savvas Papagiannidis, Eleftherios Alamanos, Michael Bourlakis, Journal of Business Research Volume 69, Issue 8, August 2016, Pages 3049-3057

the quality of the courses being delivered, the quality of the resources, technology, and equipment that support the delivery of the courses, the quality of the academic staff that design and deliver the courses, the quality of the students being accepted onto the courses, and the quality of the graduates being produced⁶.

As we can see, the brand of an HEI has different types of constituencies in order to be recognized and to gain awareness, which creates obstacles and challenges in clarifying perceptions and feelings of all stakeholders. Philipp A. Rauschnabel and others developed the University Brand Personality Scale (UBPS) based on qualitative and quantitative research conducted in Germany and the U.S.A., which consists of six dimensions: prestige, sincerity, appeal, liveliness, conscientiousness, and cosmopolitanism. The research intends to develop a widely applicable scale capable of capturing UBPS for universities in multiple countries. Managerial implications include the provision of a measure to assess university brand personality, assisting in constructing a desirable brand that helps universities attract students, faculty, sponsorships, and alumni support while working to improve the overall image of the institution (Melewar & Akel, 2005)⁷.

As the education market increases the competitiveness of a country by creating an appropriate labor force to enhance public prosperity, brand personality is certainly of great importance, as it is a framework that helps a company or organization shape the way people feel about its product, service, or mission. This results in increased brand equity and defines the brand's attitude in the marketplace. It is also a key factor in any successful marketing campaign⁸. In some cases, brand personality is confused with the brand's imagery. Here, we should remember that imagery deals with the tangible benefits of the brand, while brand personality aims to create a positive emotional perception among customers or specific market segments. The figure illustrates the five dimensions of brand personality by Aaker, demonstrating their respective attitudes.

Figure 2. Dimensions of brand personality⁹.

Due to the development of the internet and globalization, any type of organization is required to have a presence not only in the marketplace but also online, where brand personality is of great importance. No matter in which country you live or where you go, your brand should be familiar to everyone, just like the Apple brand. The Apple brand personality is centered around simplicity and the removal of complexity from people's lives; this starts from Apple stores, from how the staff dresses, the gadgets they use, and how they address the customers. Apple focuses on being a truly humanistic company with a heartfelt connection with its customers. Through these qualities, Apple is positioned as being extremely helpful to people and businesses as they strive to achieve their goals¹⁰.

Speaking about educational services, the entire management, faculty, and even the campus should illustrate care for their customers, ensuring their convenience in the learning process and making it efficient and effective. The practice and knowledge students obtain at an educational institution should serve both their prosperity and the prosperity of society in the future.

6 <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post>.

7 Philipp A. Rauschnabel, Nina Krey, Barry J. Babin, Bjoern S. Ivens, Brand management in higher education: The University Brand Personality Scale, *Journal of Business Research*, 2016

8 <https://www.investopedia.com/>

9 Aaker, J. L. (1997). Dimensions of brand personality. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34(3), 347–356

10 <https://www.outsidethesquare.com/news/brand-personality-how-to-make-your-brand-stand-out-in-the-digital-world/>

Figure 3. Brand personality is the cornerstone of effective communication – it informs the way you write, the imagery you use and the way your people behave¹¹.

As seen in the figure, all power has been directed toward making customers aware of the product or service being produced through all means of communication. The development of the internet and globalization has impacted this both positively and negatively, allowing customers to be aware of both positive and negative situations happening with the brand, influencing their point of view according to the circumstances. Additionally, information can be spread by individuals who might not always be trustworthy, sometimes even by fraudsters.

By studying the needs and wants of students, their parents, and experienced personnel, as well as digital marketing trends, ComboApp highlights ten useful techniques to use as part of an effective higher education marketing strategy: branding, search engine optimization, a great website experience, social media marketing, livestreaming, email marketing, interactive advertising, leveraging alumni and students, distance learning, and pay-per-click advertising¹².

It should be noted that all these techniques have been integrated with digital marketing, as universities should aim to align their curriculum with the emerging digital environment¹³. Managerial implications include providing a measure to assess university brand personality to assist in constructing a desirable brand that helps universities attract students, faculty, sponsorships, and alumni support while improving the overall image of the institution.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To be recognized as an equal partner by the world community and powerful states, and to enter the global market on equal terms, every country needs well-qualified and well-experienced leaders and a skilled population.

In order to have such specialists, students in tertiary education should be taught by highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities. To achieve this goal, the government is focusing on modernizing higher education, developing the social sphere, and advancing economic sectors based on cutting-edge educational technologies. This includes allowing private and foreign competitors to enter the education market.

This, in turn, increases competition among public and private higher education institutions (HEIs), as they struggle to maintain their market share, ultimately leading to a positive impact on education quality. To gain advantages in the sector, the creation and strengthening of a strong brand is the main strategic direction. A strong brand ensures the prosperity of an institution for many years.

As a key strategic direction, a strong brand helps attract more students and well-qualified faculty to the institution, enhances recognition in local and global markets, and expands market share through customer loyalty and retention.

¹¹ <https://www.outsidethesquare.com/news/brand-personality-how-to-make-your-brand-stand-out-in-the-digital-world/>

¹² <https://comboapp.com/higher-education-marketing-agency/higher-education-marketing-strategies>

¹³ Digital Marketing: The Time for a New “Academic Major” Has Arrived, Cliff Wymbs, *Journal of Marketing Education*, 33 (1) (2011), pp. 93-106.

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